

Proposed SED parameterization for LSF/PSF calibration

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ABSTRACT. It is proposed to use a set of (approximately) orthogonalized colour indices as parameters for the LSF and PSF calibrations, including chromaticity.

1 Introduction

Some sort of parameterization of the spectral energy distribution (SED) of the Gaia sources is needed both for simulation purposes and for calibration of (in particular) the LSF and PSF. We note that at least in the IDU, the chromatic image shifts must be fully taken into account in the LSF/PSF calibration, so chromaticity is implicitly included in the discussion below.

The simulations and the LSF/PSF calibration have different needs in terms of spectral resolution and realism, and it is moreover desirable to use different parameterizations for the two purposes in order to avoid circularity. This note proposes a simple set of parameters for the calibrations, derivable from the BP/RP photometry.

2 Spectrum shape coefficients

In pixel space (κ), the BP/RP spectra are separately fitted by a sum of basis functions $B_i(\kappa)$, such that the flux density (in e- per sample) is

$$S(\kappa) \simeq \sum_{i=1}^I f_i B_i(\kappa) \quad (1)$$

where $I = 4$ (TBC) is the required number of ‘bands’ in each photometer [1]. The result is a set of band fluxes f_i which define a total flux $F = \sum_i f_i$ and spectral shape parameters $s_i = f_i/F$. In the following the band fluxes f_i will be called b_i in BP, and r_i in RP, and similarly B and R will be used instead of F for the integrated fluxes.

It should be noted that B and R are not the same as the integrated BP and RP fluxes, since the fit in (1) is constrained to vanish at the endpoints.

It is assumed that b_i and r_i are somehow calibrated as functions of position and time, so that for example the ratio R/B and the spectral shape coefficients $s_i = f_i/F$ are in principle constant for a non-variable star. Effectively, this requires the definition of an instrumental system for the BP/RP photometry.

The eight band fluxes b_i, r_i (or the spectral shape coefficients) are well suited for simulation purposes, since one can compute quasi-monochromatic LSFs and PSFs for each band and obtain the polychromatic versions by simple linear combination in proportion to the fluxes. They are less suitable for calibration, however, mainly because of the likely strong degeneracies: for example, b_4 and r_1 may cover almost the same wavelength band, and there are probably too many bands for any practical calibration scheme requiring binning of the data according to the SED parameters. So it is necessary to define a reduced set of SED parameters for the calibration. It is proposed to do this via a hierarchical set of colour indices defined hereafter.

3 Colour indices

The integrated and band fluxes allow to define several colour indices. The primary colour index is¹

$$C = \ln \frac{R}{B} = \ln \frac{r_1 + r_2 + r_3 + r_4}{b_1 + b_2 + b_3 + b_4}. \quad (2)$$

The secondary colour indices are (assuming $I = 4$ bands in both BP and RP)

$$C_B = \ln \frac{b_3 + b_4}{b_1 + b_2}, \quad C_R = \ln \frac{r_3 + r_4}{r_1 + r_2}. \quad (3)$$

Tertiary indices could be defined analogously, e.g.,

$$C_{B1} = \ln \frac{b_2}{b_1}, \quad C_{B2} = \ln \frac{b_4}{b_3}, \quad C_{R1} = \ln \frac{r_2}{r_1}, \quad C_{R2} = \ln \frac{r_4}{r_3}. \quad (4)$$

With eight bands there are thus a total of seven different colour indices in a hierarchic structure.

4 A reduced set of SED parameters

It is not likely that the full set of seven colour indices is really needed for the LSF/PSF calibration. On the other hand, it is known from previous studies that a single colour index (i.e., C) will not be sufficient. Using the primary and secondary indices then seems like a reasonable compromise. Of course, this assumption should be validated.

However, there is still a problem with using the direct colour indices (C, C_B, C_R), namely the strong correlation among them: for most common stellar types, the secondary indices are mainly a function of the primary index. Using a standard library of SEDs, including representative interstellar reddening, it is possible to define the mean relations

$$C_B \simeq \bar{C}_B(C), \quad C_R \simeq \bar{C}_R(C). \quad (5)$$

Probably a linear relation is sufficient in each case, i.e., $\bar{C}_B(C) = \bar{C}_B^{(0)} + \bar{C}_B^{(1)}(C - \bar{C})$, etc.

Having adopted some mean relations, it is now possible to define a kind of ‘orthogonalized’ secondary indices by:

$$\Delta C_B = C_B - \bar{C}_B(C), \quad \Delta C_R = C_R - \bar{C}_R(C). \quad (6)$$

¹The colour indices defined here are expressed in nepers, rather than magnitudes, and are taken in the sense that redder spectra give numerically larger indices. Using magnitudes instead, if that is preferred, would not change anything in principle.

The above procedure does not take into account a possible correlation between ΔC_B and ΔC_R . A more general procedure would be to make a principal component analysis (PCA) of the set of (C, C_B, C_R) values, thus defining an orthogonal set of linear combinations of the indices. However, it is doubtful whether this is worth while compared to the conceptually simple procedure outlined above.

In the calibration process, the stars have to be binned according to their SEDs. The idea would then be to use many bins in C and relatively few bins in ΔC_B and ΔC_R , so that the discretization reflects the relative importance of the different indices, while minimizing the total number of bins. When applying the calibrations, it may on the other hand be useful to interpolate between the bins.

5 An illustration of the colour indices

By way of illustration, the colour indices C , ΔC_B , and ΔC_R were computed for a wide range of synthetic spectra, using the procedure described in [1]. The 49776 SEDs cover T_{eff} from 2000 K to 50 000 K, $\log g$ from -1.02 to $+5.5$, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ from -5.0 to $+1.0$ from the BaSeL-2.2 library, and A_V from 0 to 5 mag. The corresponding Spectrum Shape Coefficients (SSC) and other necessary information were kindly made available to the author by P. Marrese. Figures 1 and 2 show the secondary indices C_B and C_R plotted against the primary index C . The large scatter in these plots, especially for the BP data, indicates that a single colour index such as C is most likely not sufficient to parameterize this set of spectra.

Using linear regression of C_B and C_R against C , the ‘orthogonalized’ secondary indices ΔC_B and ΔC_R were then defined as

$$\Delta C_B = C_B - (-0.18 + 0.76C), \quad \Delta C_R = C_R - (+0.26 + 0.64C). \quad (7)$$

Figure 3 is a plot of ΔC_R against ΔC_B for the same set of spectra. The large scatter in this plot shows that the two indices are not strongly correlated, at least when the whole range of spectra is considered.

A tentative conclusion from this example is that at least the two indices C and ΔC_B will be required for a proper parameterization of the LSF, but possibly also ΔC_R .

References

- [1] Marrese P., Brown A., 2009: *Describing the BP/RP measurements with spectrum shape coefficients*, GAIA-C5-TN-LEI-PM-004-D (30 April 2009)

FIGURE 1: The secondary index C_B plotted against the primary index C for nearly 50 000 synthetic SEDs (see text for details). The black dots are for $\log g > 2.75$; these are plotted on top of the red dots for $\log g > 2.75$.

FIGURE 2: The secondary index C_R plotted against the primary index C for nearly 50 000 synthetic SEDs (see text for details). Colour coding as in Fig. 1.

FIGURE 3: The orthogonalized secondary indices ΔC_R and ΔC_B plotted against each other for the same spectra as in Figs. 1–2, using the same colour coding.